

Booster Disinfection Scheduling under Uncertainty in Water Distribution Systems: Approximate Robust Reformulation Approach

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32 **1. Introduction**

33 Water distribution systems (WDS) represent crucial infrastructure with significant capital
34 investment, offering society one of the most essential commodities: clean and safe drinking
35 water delivered at the necessary pressures. As the population continues to grow and the quality
36 of water sources decline, the demand for high-quality water is rapidly increases. Designing and
37 operating these systems optimally has become essential to guarantee a reliable supply of high-
38 quality water (Mala-Jetmarova et al., 2011).

39 Ensuring water quality throughout the water supply network, from source to end consumer,
40 presents a formidable challenge. Before entering the system, water undergoes treatment
41 employing a range of physical, chemical, and biological methods. The prevailing method of
42 disinfection involves the use of chlorine or chlorine-based compounds like chloramine and
43 chloride (Boccelli et al., 1998; Tryby et al., 1999). These are introduced into the water supply
44 to neutralize pathogens such as e-coli. However, over time, chlorine's effectiveness wanes as it
45 traverses the distribution network, creating difficulties in upholding adequate water quality
46 levels (Boccelli et al., 1998). To address this issue, maintaining a minimum chlorine
47 concentration at the supply line's endpoint becomes imperative (Boccelli et al., 1998).

48 Although chlorine serves as an efficient disinfectant, excessive levels of this chemical can
49 adversely impact health, and its strong taste and odour render it unsuitable for drinking. To
50 strike a proper balance, numerous countries provide guidelines establishing recommended
51 limits for chlorine concentration, typically ranging between 0.2 mg/L and 4 mg/L (Goyal and
52 Patel, 2017, 2015). When Chlorine levels introduced at water sources fall short, booster
53 stations, strategically positioned within the network, are employed to optimally enhance the
54 chlorine concentration within the supply system (Ostfeld and Salomons, 2006). The
55 optimization of the chlorine booster dosage levels has been solved by many researchers in the
56 scientific community of water researchers. Many optimization strategies have been explored
57 ranging from linear programming, linear least squares method (Boccelli et al., 1998; Tryby et
58 al., 1999), mixed integer linear programming to advance non-linear optimization techniques
59 like evolutionary and swarm intelligence algorithms in both single and multi-objective
60 frameworks (Chu et al., 2008; Harmant et al., 2000; Kang and Lansey, 2010; Ohar and Ostfeld,
61 2014; Ostfeld and Salomons, 2006; Prasad et al., 2004).

62 The intricate nature of WDS is characterized by an underlying uncertainty which also poses a
63 substantial obstacle to conventional deterministic optimization approaches used for both the

64 design and operation of these systems (Boindala et al., 2023a; Dandy et al., 2022). This
65 uncertainty stems from a multitude of factors, encompassing various dimensions, such as
66 fluctuations in demand patterns, supply dynamics, and the inherent variability of parameters
67 within water quality models (Pandey et al., 2020). Demand variability stands as one of the
68 primary sources of uncertainty within WDS (Pandey et al., 2020). Consumer water usage
69 patterns can exhibit intricate fluctuations due to factors such as seasonality, time of day, and
70 even unexpected events. Consequently, decisions related to system design and operation
71 become intricate due to the challenge of accommodating these uncertain demand patterns
72 (Boindala et al., 2022; Schwartz et al., 2016). Moreover, the intricacies of modelling water
73 quality parameters introduce another layer of uncertainty. Accurate representation of water
74 quality within a distribution system relies on numerous parameters, each with its degree of
75 variability (Kang et al., 2009; Pasha and Lansey, 2010, 2005). Parameters related to pipe
76 material, hydraulic conditions, and disinfection processes can all introduce uncertainty, making
77 it challenging to predict the exact behaviour of water quality throughout the system.

78 **1.1 Optimization under uncertainty in WDS**

79 The optimization of the design and operation of WDS under uncertainty initially focused on
80 hydraulic parameters using chance constraint formulations on demand and pressure head and
81 pipe roughness coefficient constraints (Babayan et al., 2004; Lansey et al., 1989; Sumer and
82 Lansey, 2009). Later reliability-based procedures to handle the uncertainties became popular
83 (Duan et al., 1990; Gheisi et al., 2016; Gupta and Bhawe, 1994; Su et al., 1987). Fuzzy
84 programming has also been used to solve the design problems (Geem, 2015; Shibu and Reddy,
85 2014; Vasani et al., 2022)

86 However, the realm of uncertainty pertaining to water quality parameters has received limited
87 attention. To bridge this gap, (Kang et al., 2009; Pasha and Lansey, 2010) analyse the influence
88 of select water quality parameters like bulk and wall reaction coefficients, along with pipe
89 diameters on the quality of water within the distribution systems. The study revealed a notable
90 finding: among these parameters, it was the uncertainty surrounding the bulk reaction
91 coefficient that exerted the most prominent impact on the quality of water accessible to
92 consumers. To further investigate the influence of this uncertainty surrounding the bulk-
93 reaction coefficient and its implications for the operational strategies in water quality control,
94 (Köker and Altan-Sakarya, 2015) undertook a study focused on the optimal booster disinfection
95 dosage problem. To tackle this challenge, they employed chance constraint programming,
96 formulating water quality constraints as chance constraints. This study was extended by Wang

97 and Zhu, (2021, 2022). They introduced an innovative ‘Fuzzy credibility-constrained quadratic
98 optimization approach’ and ‘inexact two-stage chance-constrained programming approach’
99 respectively. Though these stochastic optimization approaches provided good results, due to
100 the assumptions of probability distribution functions and heavy computational burden, these
101 approaches are difficult to implement. These drawbacks can be overcome by non-probabilistic
102 optimization under uncertainty techniques like robust optimization (Boindala et al., 2023b;
103 Boindala and Ostfeld, 2022). Until now, there has been a lack of research investigating non-
104 probabilistic optimization methods, like robust optimization, for tackling the challenge of
105 optimizing booster chlorination under uncertain bulk reaction coefficients.

106 This study investigates the impact of uncertain chlorine reaction rates on optimizing booster
107 disinfection doses to meet national safety standards. By introducing uncertainty into the system
108 model, it explores the relationship between robustness and dosing schedules for a reliable water
109 distribution system. The main source of uncertainty is the bulk reaction rate coefficient (k_b) of
110 chlorine. Employing a non-probabilistic robust optimization approach, which was previously
111 successful in addressing water distribution system issues, the study aims to bridge a research
112 gap in optimizing booster chlorine doses. This research strives for a dependable and resilient
113 system, adhering to quality standards while maintaining uniform and low booster dosages.

114 **1.2 Robust Optimization**

115 Traditional optimization strategies, commonly employed for designing and managing WDS,
116 face challenges when confronted with system uncertainties (Marques and Cunha, 2020). In
117 response, researchers have endeavoured to reshape conventional deterministic problem
118 formulations to accommodate these uncertainties (Mala-Jetmarova et al., 2018, 2017). One
119 effective approach to address this complexity is Robust Optimization (RO). RO offers a more
120 cautious solution by bounding uncertain parameters within standardized uncertainty sets,
121 presenting a notable advantage over worst-case methods (Ben-Tal et al., 2009). This method's
122 appeal lies in its tractability within defined uncertainty sets, such as box or ellipsoid sets,
123 providing heightened robustness and stability compared to alternative optimization techniques
124 (Bertsimas and Sim, 2004). This robustness is especially advantageous when managing noisy
125 input data or grappling with substantial, difficult-to-quantify uncertainties in the system. RO's
126 versatility has been demonstrated in addressing uncertainty within water distribution systems
127 (Boindala et al., 2023a; Boindala and Ostfeld, 2022; Pankaj et al., 2022; Perelman et al., 2013;
128 Schwartz et al., 2016).

129 **Uncertain optimization problem**

$$\min_{x \in X} f(x) \tag{1}$$

Subject to:

$$g(x, \xi) \leq 0, \forall \xi \in U \tag{2}$$

130 **Robust optimization reformulation of the above uncertain optimization problem**

$$\min_{x \in X} f(x) \tag{3}$$

Subject to:

$$\max_{\xi \in U} g(x, \xi) \leq 0 \tag{4}$$

131 In robust optimization, we intend to find the maximum value of the constraint function $g(x, \xi)$
132 within the uncertainty set U for a given value of x . If we can ensure the maximum value of
133 constraint satisfies the inequality, we ensure the constraint satisfaction for any uncertain ξ
134 within the uncertainty set U . This would ensure that the solution is feasible for all constraints
135 for every possible value of ξ and the solution is a robust-feasible solution. Now the outer
136 optimization problem is solved to obtain $x \in X$, which minimizes $f(x)$. This solution is the
137 robust optimal solution.

138 **1.3 Optimal Booster Disinfection Problem**

139 The evaluation of water quality within a (WDS) conventionally relies on the measurement of
140 residual disinfectant concentration. Chlorine is the most common disinfectant used to ensure
141 water quality in WDS. During the planning phase, the assessment of water quality involves the
142 utilization of water quality models, such as EPANET. To incorporate the bulk reaction
143 coefficient of chlorine into these models, several factors are considered, including the nature
144 of contaminants in the water, the age of the system, pipe material composition, pH levels, water
145 temperature, and various external influences. Nevertheless, the accurate prediction of these
146 parameters can prove to be a formidable task, resulting in an uncertainty in the chlorine reaction
147 coefficient parameter. This uncertainty in the reaction coefficient poses challenge in
148 determining the optimal rate of chlorine mass to be injected into the system to uphold water
149 quality standards throughout an extended operational period. The core objective of the optimal
150 booster disinfection problem is to determine the precise quantity of chlorine required for
151 injection into the system, ensuring the maintenance of the mandated residual chlorine
152 concentration levels at consumer nodes.

153 **1.4 Problem Formulation**

154 **1.4.1 The certain optimization problem**

155 A WDS's water quality is evaluated based on the deviation of residual chlorine concentration
156 levels at the sensor nodes from the standard bounds specified by the authorities. To obtain the
157 residual chlorine levels at the water quality sensor nodes, we employ a linear superposing
158 methodology proposed by Boccelli et al., (1998). The linear superposition model posits that in
159 a system featuring three booster stations denoted as A, B, and C, alongside a downstream water
160 quality sensor denoted as S, the introduction of a unit quantity of chlorine from station A
161 induces a resultant residual chlorine concentration at S termed R_A which is a response matrix
162 corresponding to chlorine injection at A. With analogous definitions applying to stations B and
163 C, we get R_B and R_C . Given the quantities x_A , x_B , and x_C representing the respective volumes
164 of chlorine introduced from stations A, B, and C, the aggregate final residual chlorine
165 concentration at S is expressed as the summation of these contributions, calculated by
166 multiplying each station's introduced volume by its associated residual concentration response
167 matrix and summing the products i.e. $x_A R_A + x_B R_B + x_C R_C$. The overall chlorine
168 concentration at S is based on the contributions of all three booster stations. These response
169 matrices are generated through extended period simulations in EPANET. As the residual
170 chlorine concentration is directly dependent on the reaction rate coefficients, the response
171 matrices also depend on the reaction rate coefficients.

172 **1.4.2 Objective Function**

173 The objective function to evaluate the water quality (i.e., residual chlorine concentration) at
174 each sensor node and for each time-period is defined based on a penalty function proposed by
175 (Ewald et al., 2008; Kurek and Ostfeld, 2012) as described in figure-1. This is a different
176 approach that does not put strict bounds [C_{lower} , C_{upper}] for the residual chlorine concentration.
177 The objective here is to ensure the deviations of the residual chlorine from the desired value
178 C_0 are minimized.

179

180 Figure 1 Water quality penalty function proposed by Kurek et al., 2012

181 The objective used in this study for residual chlorine concentration can be expressed as follows
 182 (Equation 5)

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^+} F(x), \quad F(x) = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} F_q(C_n(t)) \quad (5)$$

183 Where N_s is the set of sensor nodes, F_q is the penalty function described in figure-1, $C_n(t)$ is
 184 the residual chlorine concentration at node $n \in N_s$, time $t \in T$, and T is the set of time periods.
 185 Each of the piece-wise linear penalty function described in figure-1 can be rewritten as shown
 186 in Equation 6. Here f_i are the individual linear functions where $a_1 = a_4 = F_{mean}$, $a_2 = a_3 = 0$,
 187 $b_1 = P_1$, $b_2 = \frac{F_{mean}}{C_o - C_{lower}}$, $b_3 = \frac{F_{mean}}{C_{upper} - C_o}$, $b_4 = -P_2$, $C_1 = C_{lower}$, $C_2 = C_3 = C_o$, $C_4 = C_{upper}$.

$$F_q(C_n(t)) = \max_{i=1,2,3,4} f_i, \text{ where } f_i = a_i + b_i(C_i - C_n(t)) \quad (6)$$

188 By using Equation 6, The certain optimization problem can be reformulated to eliminate the
 189 maximum function as follows (Equations 7-12).

190

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^+} \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} z_{t,n} \quad (7)$$

Subject to:

$$f_1(C_n(t)) \leq z_{t,n}, \forall t \in T, n \in N_s \quad (8)$$

$$f_2(C_n(t)) \leq z_{t,n}, \forall t \in T, n \in N_s \quad (9)$$

$$f_3(C_n(t)) \leq z_{t,n}, \forall t \in T, n \in N_s \quad (10)$$

$$f_4(C_n(t)) \leq z_{t,n}, \forall t \in T, n \in N_s \quad (11)$$

$$c_n(t) = R_n(t) * x, n \in NS, x \geq 0 \quad (12)$$

191 Here $R_n(t)$ is the response matrix (R) of sensor node (n) for a particular time (t).

192 1.4.3 The uncertain optimization problem

193 1.4.3.1 Uncertain parameters and the uncertainty set

194 In this research, the decision variables are the concentration of chlorine dosage denoted as x_{it} ,
 195 which was administered at each booster station 'i' during a given time interval 't'. The
 196 uncertain parameter in this study is the chlorine first-order bulk reaction rate coefficient,
 197 denoted as ' k_b ', utilized within the EPANET model for conducting water quality computations.
 198 Other hydraulic and water quality parameters are assumed to be deterministic. The uncertainty
 199 in the reaction rate coefficients (k_b) induces uncertainty in the corresponding response
 200 matrices.

201 1.4.3.2 Ellipsoidal vs Box uncertainty set

202 The instances of the uncertain parameter are assumed to belong to an uncertainty set. A feasible
 203 solution to the uncertain optimization problem should be feasible for all the constraints
 204 generated from each instance of the uncertain variable in the uncertainty set.

205 A box uncertainty set is the ∞ -norm unit circle in n-dimensions. For the box uncertainty set
 206 the extreme uncertain parameter values k_b , which occur at the corners of the box, correspond
 207 to extreme values of the response matrices (Boindala et al., 2023a). Furthermore, the different
 208 components of uncertain parameter can take values independent of each other. Thus, it is easier
 209 to identify the corners of a box uncertainty set. For example, let the uncertain parameter be $x \in$
 210 \mathbb{R}^2 and let the box be defined by $\mathcal{U} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^2: \|x\|_\infty \leq 1\}$. That is, the uncertainty set is the
 211 square defined by the lines $-1 \leq x_1 \leq 1$ and $-1 \leq x_2 \leq 1$. The corners of \mathcal{U} are
 212 $(-1, -1), (-1, 1), (1, -1)$ and $(1, 1)$.

213 An ellipsoidal uncertainty set is more complicated and is defined by a n-dimensional ellipsoid.
214 For an ellipsoidal uncertainty set, it is hard to define a corner. The ellipsoidal uncertainty set is
215 complicated in another way as well. At the boundary, defined by the ellipsoid, the different
216 components of the uncertain parameter are related to each other unlike the box uncertain set
217 where at the boundary the different components can take (feasible) values independent of each
218 other. For example, let the uncertain parameter be $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and let the ellipsoid be the unit disc
219 defined by $\mathcal{U} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^2: \|x\|_2 \leq 1\}$. That is, the uncertainty set is the set of points in the circle
220 centered at the origin of radius 1. The maximum (or minimum) value that a component can
221 achieve is 1(or -1) but then the other component will become 0, the maximum value achieved
222 by both the components together is $(1/\sqrt{2}, 1/\sqrt{2})$, and the minimum value achieved by both
223 the components together is $(-1/\sqrt{2}, -1/\sqrt{2})$.

224 Thus, an ellipsoidal uncertainty set asks for a more involved approach to obtain the response
225 matrices to be used in the optimization problem. We first opted to use a surrogate model, a
226 function of the reaction rate, to replace the response matrices in the optimization problem. This
227 method failed for multiple time periods and a large sized network owing to the large number
228 of response matrix components to regress for. The approach we use in this paper is to develop
229 an approximate robust reformulation.

230 **1.4.3.3 Approximate Robust Reformulation**

231 In pursuit of a more refined solution, we have chosen to adopt an ellipsoidal uncertainty set for
232 the bulk reaction coefficient. It is worth noting that the variability in these coefficients
233 propagates into the uncertainty surrounding the response matrices. Due to the intricate
234 relationship between the bulk reaction coefficients and the response matrices, quantifying the
235 uncertainty set of the response matrices poses a significant challenge. However, leveraging our
236 domain knowledge, we can infer that the extreme values of the response matrices will manifest
237 at points situated along the boundary of the ellipsoidal uncertainty set for the bulk reaction
238 coefficients.

239 First, we sample a set of boundary points (BP). We subsequently generate response matrices
240 for each of these sample points. Armed with these collections of response matrices, we address
241 the optimization problem by incorporating constraints corresponding to all of them. This
242 process results in the formulation of the approximate robust reformulation, as presented in
243 Equations (13-18).

$$\min_x \max_{p \in \text{BP}} (F(x, p)) = \min_x \max_{p \in \text{BP}} \left(\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} z_{t,n}^p \right) \quad (13)$$

Subject to:

$$f_1(c_n(t, p)) \leq z_{t,n}^p \quad \forall t \in T, n \in N_s, p \in \text{BP} \quad (14)$$

$$f_2(c_n(t, p)) \leq z_{t,n}^p \quad \forall t \in T, n \in N_s, p \in \text{BP} \quad (15)$$

$$f_3(c_n(t, p)) \leq z_{t,n}^p \quad \forall t \in T, n \in N_s, p \in \text{BP} \quad (16)$$

$$f_4(c_n(t, p)) \leq z_{t,n}^p \quad \forall t \in T, n \in N_s, p \in \text{BP} \quad (17)$$

$$c_n(t, p) = \tilde{B}_n(t, p) * x, \quad \forall n \in N_s, \forall t \in T, \forall p \in \text{BP} \quad (18)$$

244

245 **2. Methodology**

246 The methodology is explained with the help of a flowchart in the figure-2. The initial step is to
 247 generate a set of random boundary sample points (BP) of the ellipsoidal uncertainty set for the
 248 uncertain bulk reaction coefficient (k_b). Using these boundary sample points, we will
 249 approximately estimate the uncertain response matrices which are then used in the approximate
 250 robust reformulation shown in (Equations 13-18). The procedure for sampling the boundary
 251 points in the ellipsoidal set is explained in the appendix section. The response matrices are
 252 estimated from EPANET simulations, the methodology for estimation of the response matrices
 253 through extended period water quality simulations is explained in detail in (Boccelli et al.,
 254 1998; Boindala et al., 2023a; Köker and Altan-Sakarya, 2015; Tryby et al., 1999). After the
 255 estimation of the response matrices, the problem defined in (Equations 13-18) is solved using
 256 a non-linear solver ‘fmincon’ and the robust booster schedule for booster disinfection injection
 257 is estimated that ensures minimal deviations from the desired residual disinfectant
 258 concentration.

259 This obtained robust solution is verified by subjecting the system to various values of the
 260 reaction rate coefficients using Monte-Carlo sampling within the uncertainty set while
 261 following the optimal dosages obtained previously and estimating the residual chlorine
 262 penalties using the Kurek penalty function. The solution is said to be robust if and only if the
 263 maximum penalty obtained from the sampling points is equal to or less than the penalty
 264 obtained through the approximate robust reformulation.

265

266

Figure 2 Methodology Flowchart

267 **3. Case Study**

268 **3.1 EPANET NET-1 (Network system-1)**

269 A small-scale WDS named "NET-1" within the EPANET WDS analysis software is considered
 270 as the first case study. This WDS comprises a network of 10 interconnected nodes linked by
 271 12 pipes. It includes a reservoir with a water level of 243.8 meters and a pump capable of a
 272 maximum flow rate of 189.3 litres per second, with a shutoff head value of 101.3 meters.
 273 Notably, Node 10 houses an elevated cylindrical storage tank with a diameter of 15.4 meters,
 274 situated at a ground level of 259.1 meters. The primary purpose of this WDS is to supply water
 275 to eight consumers situated at nodes 1 through 8. These consumers exhibit base demands
 276 ranging from 6.5 to 13 litres per second. The demand multipliers for these consumers vary from

277 0.4 to 1.6. Additionally, the pipes in the system have assumed roughness coefficients set at
278 100. For a visual representation of this WDS, please refer to figure-3.

279

280 Figure 3 Graphical representation of Network system -1 which is 'NET-1' example in
281 EPANET

282 3.2 Fossolo Network (Network system-2)

283 The Fossolo Network (FOS) was inspired from the WDS of the Fossolo neighborhood, in
284 Bologna, Italy. It reflects the water distribution system that lies beneath it. This network
285 handles a demand of 3,000 cubic meters (CMD) and was studied by Bragalli et al. In 2008 as
286 part of a their comprehensive design study. You can find a representation of the system's layout
287 in figure 4. The FOS network consists of 58 pipes 36 demand nodes and a reservoir which is
288 maintained a consistent head level of 121.00 meters. It's worth noting that all the pipes in this
289 network are made of high density polyethylene with a roughness coefficient of 150, which is
290 relatively high. To account for variation in the demand levels within the system a demand
291 pattern has been incorporated where demand multipliers range from 0.4 to 1.6 – similar, to
292 what is used in the NET 1 example.

Figure 4 Graphical representation of network system-2 which is a benchmark network proposed by Bragalli et al., 2008

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 EPANET NET-1

For the current study, we assume residual chlorine bounds to be between 0.2mg/l and 4mg/l (Goyal and Patel, 2017; Köker and Altan-Sakarya, 2015). The network is simulated for 480 hours to ensure hydraulic stability and periodicity and the water quality readings from the last 24 hours are considered for the response matrices generation which are in turn used for analysis and optimization. Four different booster location configurations and three different sizes of ellipsoidal uncertainty set $\{[-0.2,-0.8], [-0.3,-0.7], [-0.4,0.6]\}$ are considered for the analysis. Here the size represents the maximum and minimum values of the reaction rate coefficients within the ellipsoidal set. The covariance matrix for the generation of the ellipsoidal sets is assumed to be random. The Kurek penalty function parameters used for the analysis are $P1 = 1000, P2 = 500, F_{\text{mean}} = 5, C_o = 0.5, C_{\text{lower}} = 0.2, C_{\text{upper}} = 4$ refer to Equation 6. For each of the cases (refer to Table-1), we report our schedule and compare the cost of our solution to the maximum cost obtained from Monte Carlo simulations. For $[-0.2, -0.8]$ range of reaction coefficients, the four different booster configurations and their optimal schedules are shown in figures-5,6. The schedules for remaining ranges are moved to the appendix (figures-12,13).

312 The results clearly indicate the dependency of booster location configuration in the optimal
 313 schedules and also in the optimal penalty function value.

314 Table 1 Different cases examined for network system-1

	Range of the reaction rate coefficients (k_b)
Network system-1 Case-1	[-0.8,-0.2]
Network system-1 Case-2	[-0.7,-0.3]
Network system-1 Case-3	[-0.6,-0.4]

315

316 Figure 5 Different booster configurations (a,b,c,d for the network system-1)

317

318 Figure 6 Optimal booster dosage schedules for all the four different booster configurations of
 319 network system -1

320 **4.2 Fossolo Network**

321 FOS is traditionally subjected to a single loading condition, which is available in the network
 322 database of the University of Kentucky (Ormsbee et al., 2022). To analyse this system for
 323 multiple loadings in order to perform extended period simulation, the demand patterns of NET-
 324 1 example of EPANET are used. Similar to network system 1, the system was simulated for
 325 480 hours and the water quality readings from the last 24 hours are used for generating the
 326 response matrices. Four different booster configurations and three different ellipsoidal sizes
 327 similar to Network system-1 are considered for analysis (Table-2). Four different nodes are
 328 considered for water quality measurements (Nodes =2,4,6,8). The Kurek penalty function

329 parameters used for the analysis are $P1 = 10, P2 = 5, F_{\text{mean}} = 5, C_o = 0.5, C_{\text{lower}} =$
 330 $0.2, C_{\text{upper}} = 4$. For each of the cases, the obtained robust booster schedule is reported and the
 331 cost of the solution is compared with the maximum cost obtained through Monte Carlo
 332 simulations. The optimal schedule obtained for each of these cases is also reported. The four
 333 different booster configurations and their optimal schedules for $[-0.2,-0.8]$ ellipsoidal size are
 334 graphically shown in figure-7,8. The schedules for other sizes are moved to the appendix
 335 (figures 14,15). The results clearly indicate the effect of booster location configuration in the
 336 optimal schedules and also in the optimal penalty function value.

337 Table 2 Different cases examined for network system-2

	Range of the reaction rate coefficients (k_b)
Network system-2 Case-1	$[-0.8,-0.2]$
Network system-2 Case-2	$[-0.7,-0.3]$
Network system-2 Case-3	$[-0.6,-0.4]$

338

Legend:	⊗ Booster Station-1	⊗ Booster Station-2
⊗ Booster Station-3	⊗ Booster Station-4	● Sensor Node

340

341

Figure 7 Four different booster configurations (a,b,c,d) for network system-2

342

343 Figure 8 Optimal booster schedules for ellipsoidal set of size $[-0.2, -0.8]$ for network system-2

344 4.3 Sensitivity analysis

345 The observations illuminate the substantial impact of booster station location configurations
 346 on both the optimal booster injection schedule and the penalty-based objective function. To
 347 conduct a more in-depth analysis regarding the sensitivities of several critical assumptions
 348 made in our prior examination, we have assessed select parameters within the context of Case-
 349 2 booster configurations of FOS (network system-2).

350 4.3.1 Effect of Varying the Desired Residual Chlorine Concentration C_0

351 For this sensitivity analysis, the lower and upper bounds of residual chlorine are set as $[0.2, 4]$
 352 mg/L. The desired residual chlorine level was varied between four different values $C_0 \in$
 353 $\{0.5, 1, 1.5, 2\}$. The network was subjected to variation of the reaction rate coefficient in an
 354 ellipsoidal uncertainty set of size $\{-0.2, -0.8\}$. The total mass injected into the system as well

355 as the objective function values were compared, as shown in figure-9. The variation of the
 356 desired residual chlorine concentration had a significant effect on both the total chlorine mass
 357 injection as well as the penalty-based objective function. A unique trend of increase and
 358 decrease was observed in the objective function values or total mass injected. As the C_0 value
 359 is moving closer to the centre of the safety region, the system benefits from an increase in the
 360 residual chlorine levels which would indirectly require an increase of booster injection mass
 361 into the system. But as the C_0 value is almost equal to the centre of the safety region; the system
 362 does not benefit from high residual chlorine levels which in turn reduced the mass injected into
 363 the system compared to $C_0 = 1.5$.

364

365

366 Figure 9 Effect of varying the desired residual chlorine concentration (C_0)

367 4.3.2 Effect of Residual Chlorine Regulation Limits

368 We consider the same configuration-2 booster configuration within FOS. In this study the water
 369 quality regulatory limits are changed to investigate its effect on the optimization methodology
 370 while keeping the other sensitive parameters constant. Specifically, four distinct limit
 371 scenarios, denoted as $\{[0.2, 1], [0.2, 1.5], [0.2, 2], [0.2, 4]\}$, were explored. Figure-10 shows a
 372 comparison of the results of the total mass injected into the system and variations in the
 373 objective function across these scenarios. The width of the feasibility region played a pivotal
 374 role in influencing these parameters. The findings illustrate a clear trend. As the width of
 375 feasibility region is increased, we observe an increase in the injected mass and a decrease in

376 the penalty associated. As the desired concentration is fixed to $C_o = 0.5$, with the increase in the
 377 upper limits of the feasibility region we decrease the slope of f_3 curve in the penalty function
 378 which would increase the benefit of the system to have higher chlorine concentrations. This in
 379 turn resulted in increase in the mass injected into the system and decrease in the penalty
 380 function.

381

382 Figure 10 Effect of varying the water quality regulation limits.

383 4.3.3 Effect of Kurek penalty function values (P_1 & P_2)

384 The sensitivity analysis in this section focuses on penalty coefficients or the slope of the penalty
 385 functions (P_1 & P_2), namely f_1 and f_4 . The f_1 function represents penalties associated with
 386 residual chlorine deviations below the lower limit of water quality regulation, while f_4 pertains
 387 to residual chlorine deviations above the upper limit. Using the same configuration-2 in
 388 network system-2, we explore five distinct sets of $\{P_1, P_2\}$ values, specifically: $\{10,500\}$,
 389 $\{10,50\}$, $\{10,5\}$, $\{100,5\}$. This analysis involves a comparison of the mass injected under each
 390 set of penalty coefficients.

391 It is notable that the initial increase in the injected mass corresponds to a reduction in the
 392 penalty coefficient of P_2 , which governs the penalties for deviations from the upper quality
 393 limit. Conversely, the subsequent decrease in the last two cases can be attributed to an increase
 394 in the penalty coefficient of P_1 . These observations underscore the substantial impact of

395 penalty functions on the optimization of schedules, highlighting the importance of judiciously
396 selecting penalty coefficients in the decision-making process figure-11.

397

398 Figure 11 Effect of Kurek penalty function values (P_1 & P_2)

399 5. Conclusions

400 This study centres on the integration of uncertain chlorine reaction rate coefficients into water
401 quality management, a task imbued with complexity due to the intricate interplay between these
402 coefficients and the response matrices. Quantifying the uncertainty set for these matrices
403 presents a formidable challenge. To tackle this issue effectively we employ an Approximate
404 Robust Reformulation approach, offering a pragmatic solution for handling uncertain reaction
405 rates and optimizing the scheduling of chlorine booster stations. The uncertain response
406 matrices are derived through an extended period simulation (EPS) of water quality simulations,
407 using EPANET. This response matrix serves as a surrogate model, effectively supplanting the
408 need for computationally intensive EPANET simulations. It is important to note that in the
409 absence of constraints on residual chlorine concentration at sensor nodes, there exists the
410 possibility of this resulting in solutions with residual chlorine concentrations exceeding
411 acceptable chlorine regulation limits.

412 Given the inherent non-linearity of the problem, it tends to produce local minima solutions. To
413 verify the precision of the approximation methodology, comprehensive validations are
414 undertaken through Monte Carlo simulations, thereby ensuring the resilience and dependability
415 of the proposed approach. Furthermore, a sensitivity analysis is conducted focusing on a
416 booster configuration-2 on FOS. The results illuminate the substantial impact of these

417 parameters on both the total mass injected into the system and the objective function value,
418 underscoring their significance in optimizing the water distribution system. This analysis offers
419 valuable insights into the complex dynamics of water quality management under uncertain
420 conditions.

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424 **Authors Contributions**

425 *S.P.B.* played a pivotal role in the conceptualization, methodology development, coding
426 implementation, result generation, results interpretation, and paper writing.

427 *G.J.* significantly contributed to conceptualization, methodology, and paper writing.

428 *A.O.* served as the guide, contributing to conceptualization, methodology, and paper writing.

429

430 **Availability of data and materials**

431 The data used in the article will be provided upon request to the corresponding author.

432

433 **Competing Interests**

434 The authors declare no competing interests.

435

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575

576 **Appendix**

577 MATLAB code for generation of points on the boundary of the ellipsoidal uncertainty set

```
RandMatrix = randn(dim); %dim is the number of uncertain parameters or uncertain
%parameter dimensions
PDSymmetricRandomMatrix = RandMatrix*RandMatrix'; %Generate a co-variance matrix,
%here its generated randomly but it can be replaced by a known matrix
CoVarMa = PDSymmetricRandomMatrix;
r = 1;
A = CoVarMa;
L = chol(A)';
NOP = 100;
UB = 1; LB = -1;
% Generate random data
x = LB*ones(NOP,dim) + (UB-LB)*rand(NOP,dim);
% Calculate z
z = sqrt(sum(x.^2, 2));
z = repmat(z, 1, dim);
% Transform data
y = x ./ z * r;
y_new = L * y';
% Scaling to [-0.8,-0.2]
Bound = [-0.2,-0.8]; % these bounds represent the size of an ellipse or the lower and upper
% values the uncertain parameter can take
UB =Bound(1); LB = Bound(2);
Y_new_UL = max(y_new,[],2);
y_new_LL = min(y_new,[],2);
range_Y_new = max(y_new,[],2)-min(y_new,[],2);
Normalized_y_new = (y_new-y_new_LL)./range_Y_new;
Y_Scaled = LB +Normalized_y_new*(UB-LB);
y_new = Y_Scaled; % Boundary points on the ellipse
```


579

Figure 12 Optimal booster schedules for Network system -1 subjected to variations in the

580

bulk reaction coefficient within the ellipsoidal set size $[-0.3,-0.7]$

Figure 13 Optimal booster schedules for Network system -1 subjected to variations in the bulk reaction coefficient within the ellipsoidal set size [-0.4,-0.6]

584

585

Figure 14 Optimal booster schedules for Network system -2 subjected to variations in the

586

bulk reaction coefficient within the ellipsoidal set size $[-0.3, -0.7]$

587

588

589

Figure 15 Optimal booster schedules for Network system -2 subjected to variations in the bulk reaction coefficient within the ellipsoidal set size $[-0.4,-0.6]$

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